

The Development of a Visual Reference Database for Product Designers' Use

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Abstract

Sources of inspiration play an important role in the design process, both in defining the context for designs and in informing the creation of individual designs. The initial study of this research is to understand the role visual references currently play within the design process, in order to develop a classification of image types and reference keywords to construct an electronic image database for professional use in product design.

A series of interviews to product design professionals and a workshop were carried out as part of this research. It identified that product images form the majority of visual references used by designers as they provide more context than other images.

According to the survey, to understand the sources of inspiration, visual references could be classified from three different aspects:

1. Function of images: reasons why designers use images, e.g. communication, inspiration
2. Content of images: what is an image physically presenting
3. Context of images: additional information conveyed by the image

The information derived from the classification is then analysed into tangible and conceptual categories; for example, colour and material are tangible categories, and characteristic and value are conceptual categories. Tangible properties are readily stored in the database using standard descriptors whereas conceptual properties require keywords that identify properties of emotions and characteristics .

In summary, the research shows how a framework of keywords, which identifies the tangible and conceptual qualities of images in the database, has been developed .

Keywords: Product design, Visual language, Visual references, Emotion, Characteristic

Introduction

The use of information is fundamental to the design process. According to Formosa (1991), an insufficient flow of information leads to inadequately designed products and he believes that information could enhance the design process; in the proper environment it will feed creativity. Designers frequently search for and use information to help them to construct new knowledge related to the design topic, simultaneously searching for new information that will help to determine design constraints and produce a satisfactory design (Lahti et al., 2000). Even Eckert and Stacey (2000) indicated that “the source of inspiration plays an important role in the design process, both in defining the context for new designs and in informing the creation of individual designs.”

There have been several investigations into the method of gathering appropriate resources for designers to improve creativity and design solutions. Most research focuses on providing users with information to fulfil a need. Design today is recognised as a critical factor in the industry and in the marketplace. Therefore, more information is needed within the design process other than for example ergonomics or engineering. The subject of this paper is an image databank based on computer technology to give designers visual access to information easily and quickly.

Previously most classification of products has been done by type, as in the Design Index (Appendix A). However, it is argued here that consideration should be given to categorisation on other functional bases, such as; controls, colour, material, shape, texture.

According to Baxter (1995), visual references were taken as a designers' approach to explore the concept within the design process. Mono (1997), commented that a designer should aim at understanding product language better to be able to improve his design. If that is correct, a visual reference based on a classification by product language would provide designers with more inspiration. The initial study of this research is to understand the role visual references currently play within the design process, in order to develop a classification of image types and reference keywords to construct an electronic image database for professional use in product design.

Survey of Designers

A series of interviews with product design professionals and a workshop were carried out as part of this research. The survey was based on an investigation of how product designers discuss and categorise visual design sources. It also collected information about the role visual material currently plays in the design process within practical design territory. The designers were shown selected products and images and their comments, reactions and descriptions recorded. There was no specific principle for the selection of products and images, because designers, according to the literature research, access highly varied products and images to gain experiences and knowledge. The selected products were easy to carry to the interview and the selected images were randomly picked from the book of *Notable Product Design* and the image providers, Digital Vision (Figure 1). The survey was carried out by interviewing 17 designers based in London. Their professional experiences range from 3 years to 35 years.

Figure 1, Products and images used for the interview

Descriptive Language

The value of an image may be enhanced by its linguistic associations through descriptions and keywords which identify and interpret its content. For this reason, the relationship between language and images will be discussed in this section.

Image language structure

Analysis of all the designers' responses showed that the language they used to discuss the images and products could be synthesised into:

- 1) The object + adjective

This product is ergonomically designed; the handle is very ergonomic.

It is **functional**. It is designed with a **geometrical form**.

- 2) The object + sense + adjective

This product **looks** fun.

It **looks/feels** heavy. It tries to **show** quality.

It **looks** cheap. The material **looks/feels** warm.

- 3) Style

This is **1980's design**.

This is **Bauhaus Style**. It reminds me of **Memphis**.

- 4) The function of product

It is **portable**. It seems you can **open it**. It is comfortable to **hold**.

- 5) A description/interpretation.

It is **house ware**. It is **furniture**.

- 6) Cause and result

It is a good/bad design, **because** the graphic is too small.

The colour is very strong **so** it looks very modern.

Linguistic analysis shows that nouns and adjectives are the main classes used in dialog (Eckert and Stacey 2002) and this has been reflected in analysis of the designers' comments. However, the number of keywords recorded in the survey is contrary to Eckert and Stacey's observations with the range of nouns used in the survey being comparatively small, while the range of adjectives is large and open-ended.

Image descriptions

The responses showed that designers' descriptions could be divided into Subjective and Objective responses.

- Objective responses describe the tangible information in an image or physical properties of a product. They provide a general introduction to an image or a product. For example, "the handle is ergonomic", and responses are based upon fact or rational experiences and how it meets functional needs.
- Subjective responses are emotional responses and can be divided into direct and indirect. Direct responses are essentially feelings which are an emotional reaction to an image or a product. For example, "it is **comfortable**". Indirect responses are associated feelings which are caused by a part of an image context or a product property (Figure 2). For example, "this function is **clever**".

Figure 2, Classification of Image descriptions

Image Functions

The interviewees stated that anything can be a source of inspiration. However, images function not only as inspiration sources, but also as an essential medium within the design process.

According to the responses, using images is a powerful way to express complex ideas quickly

to a non-designer. The reasons for using visual references within the design process are to:

- Communicate with clients
- Understand consumers
- Assist in expressing the themes of the project
- Understand the related environments
- Look for inspiration or functional solutions.

These possibilities are all used to enhance the designers' visualisation of the product's design. These possibilities also relate to Eckert and Stacey's (2002) statement that "previous designs and other sources of ideas furnish a vocabulary both for thinking about new designs and for describing designs to others."

Image Content

The focus of this research is a visual database for use by product designers and in this context images can be split into PRODUCT and NON-PRODUCT:

1) PRODUCT images

This means the image contains an individual product or a collection of products (Figure 3). It may also only contain details of a product or an image with specific information such as material, texture or function.

Figure 3, Product Images

2) NON-PRODUCT images

The images in this category cover a substantially wide range of subject matter (Figure 3) such as users, environments, and art works. Designers give the images specific definitions and use them to present a subject or a theme.

Figure 4, Non-Product Images

The survey also indicated that information used from images includes product properties such as materials, product context such as values, design elements such as colours and image concept such as emotions. This information has been classified and represented in Figure 5 below.

Figure 5, Structure of Image Classification

The information derived from the classification may also be grouped into tangible information and conceptual information (Figure 6). The diagram shows that tangible information is about product properties such as colour, form and so on and product market segmentations.

Figure 6, Classification of Image Information

This information is typically used in a design brief and hence can be seen as forming a product specification. The term “SPECIFICATION” (see Figure 9) has therefore been adopted to describe tangible information about the context of an image.

Conceptual information, however, is a construct of tangible information interpreted by the viewer. Observations from the interview with designers indicated that the interaction between an image and a designer's view can be represented as Figure 7. A viewer can receive information not only about the properties of an image, but also about its representation, because images of objects already have some interpretation attached to them in the way they have been created (Ecker and Stacey 2000). The emotional reaction of the viewer to the image will be influenced by this interpretation.

Figure 7, The relation between an image and a viewer

Desmet (2002) proposed the concept of affective states (Table 1) to understand the relationship between a person and an object. He divided these into emotions and moods, emotions being intentional (i.e. the observer's reaction), acute and usually elicited by an explicit cause, while moods having a relatively long-term character with essentially non-intentional (i.e. information content in the object) and combined causes. In the context of image analyses for the visual database, the viewer's initial responses to an image will be the emotional responses, while more considered analyses of the information in the image will result in the moods responses. The latter will use the conceptual information identified in Figure 6.

	Intentional	Non-intentional
Acute	Emotion	Mood
Dispositional	Sentiments	Emotional traits

Table 1, Differentiating affective states (Source: Desmet (2002), *Design Emotions*)

Combining Figures 2 and 6 into Figure 8 demonstrates that conceptual information embraces

not only the subjective data but also some objective. The objective responses included are Features and Lifestyles, while Value, Quality and Emotion are the subjective responses.

Figure 8, The relationship between Image information & Image descriptions

Figure 8 also shows that the totality of information derived from an image may be grouped into three areas. SPECIFICATION information is objective, tangible information. CHARACTERISTIC information is subjective, conceptual information which may be identified by Desmet’s affective state of Mood and includes Features, Value, Lifestyle and Quality. EMOTION information is Desmet’s affective state of emotion – the viewer’s initial response to an image.

Figure 9, The three information areas of an Image

Cupchik (2000) explained that industrial design objects have stimulus oriented and response oriented perspectives; stimuli are provided by the content of objects and the observer responds to these. According to this, SPECIFICATION and CHARACTERISTIC areas provide the information eliciting the EMOTION responses.

Classifying Keywords

Keywords form the main element used in the database to define an image. They will be grouped within the three information areas and displayed in different categories in the visual reference database. In order to avoid users taking too much time when selecting keywords, and to avoid confusion, the keywords will need to be clearly understandable.

Specification

This information area covers product properties and market segmentations. The categories were derived from selected research sources. Categories include: Colour, Form, Material, Texture, Users, Places/activities and Product fields (Table 2). The members of Colour, Form, Material, and Texture were selected from studies by Flurschein, 1983, Manzini, 1986, Wong, 1993, Gasson, 1974, Bevlin, 1977, Lefteri, 2001, and Danger, 1987. Members of each category were selected by their distinguishable visual quality and general descriptive terms. For instance, plastics could be divided into PP, ABS, Acetate and so on, however, the generic descriptor ‘plastics’ was selected as a member. Members of Users, Places/activities, and Product field were selected from market research data groupings (Kotler, 2000, Doyle, 1998, and Lambin, 2000). Some of these may not familiar to designers and will be modified as the visual reference database develops.

Categories	Material	Colour	Form	Texture	Users	Places /activities	Product Field
Members	Steel/Iron	Violet group	Representational	Smooth	Gender	Home	Electric
	Stainless steels	Blue group	Natural/organic	Rough	Male	Office	Domestic
	Aluminium	Blue-green group	Man-made	Soft	Female	School	Furnisher
	Copper	Green group	Verbal	Hard	Age	Public space	Transport
	Glass	Yellow group	Abstract		Under 6	Out door	Medical
	Rubber	Orange group	Calligraphic		6-11	Sport	
	Wood	Brown group	Geometric		12-19	Water sport	
	Plastics	Red group	Others		20-34	Winter sport	
	Ceramics/Porcelain	Pink group			35-49	Restaurant	
	Composite and compound materials	Grey group			50-64		
	Others	White			65+		
		Black			Class		
		Others			Upper Uppers		
					Lower Uppers		
					Upper Middles		
					Middle Class		
				Working Class			
				Upper Lower			
				Lower Lower			

Table 2, Categories and members of SPECIFICATION

Emotion

This information area is intended to provide users with a record of their emotional reactions to

images. Because most images are product images and the vocabularies to express emotions so varied, the emotion keywords adopted are taken from Desmet's (2002) study of product emotions. It includes 14 members: Indignation, Contempt, Disgust, Unpleasant surprise, Dissatisfaction, Disappointment, Boredom, Desire, Pleasant surprise, Inspiration, Amusement, Admiration, Satisfaction, and Fascination.

Characteristic

For this information area 120 keywords were selected from the interviews. Many words were often repeated such as *friendly*, *nice*, *ergonomic*, and *technical* etc. From a linguistic perspective, the representation of the meaning of a word is called a '**concept**' (Seiler and Wannemacher 1983). 'A **concept** for a kind of entities is information in the mind that allow us to discriminate entities of that kind from entities of other kinds (Löbner, 2000: 20). In order to classify keywords effectively, they were firstly categorised by their concepts which were taken from Roget's Interactive Thesaurus. Usually, a word has more than one concept so the criterion for choosing a concept was general use. For example, *fantastic* has concepts of **difference**, **quantity**, and **superiority**; **superiority** was selected.

Furthermore, there are a few words whose concepts are not the same in the thesaurus when used in contemporary verbal communication (e.g. *awkward* is not suitable as the concept of **inability**, **difficulty**, and **unsocial action**, when using it to describe a product or design.) Categorising words by their concepts assists in grouping them together, as a method of clarifying their meanings. For example, **classic**, **fantastic**, **genius**, **great**, and **impressive** are in the same keyword category and share the concept of **superiority**.

The keywords were split into Subjective and Objective, using the definition from Collins English Dictionary:

- Objective:
 1. existing independently of perception or an individual's conceptions.
 2. undistorted by emotion or personal bias.
 3. of or relating to actual and external phenomena as opposed to thoughts, feelings, etc

- Subjective:
 1. belonging to, proceeding from, or relating to the mind of the thinking subject and

not the nature of the object being considered. 2. of, relating to, or emanating from a person's emotions, prejudices, etc. 3. relating to the inherent nature of a person or thing; essential. 4. existing only as perceived and not as a thing in itself.

They were then grouped into second levels such as positive and negative under subjective; physical and behaviour under objective. The sub-levels were then developed by manipulating the keywords into natural groups. As a result, there were ten subjective categories and 22 objective categories (Table 3 & Table 4). Some words which were ambiguous in that they could either be Subjective or Objective were re-categorised after the categories had been designed.

Heading Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Keyword
Subjective	Feelings	Physical sensation	Cold, Comfortable, Cosy, Relax
		Liking	Appreciated, Simulated
		Specificity	Different, Individual, Particular, Special
		Interestingness	Interesting, Exciting
	Positive	Kindness	Peaceful
		Beauty	Attractive, Beautiful, Cute, Fascinating
		Superiority	Classic, Clever, Fantastic, Cool, Impressive, Great, Genius
		Quality	Good, Nice, High quality
	Negative	Happiness	Happy, Fun, Cheerful, Satisfied, Recreated, Playful
		Negative	Awkward, Bizarre, Boring, Disappoint, Horrible, Ugly, Weak, Unnecessary, Confusing

Table 3, Categories of subjective keywords

Heading Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Keyword
Objective	Physical	Visual features	Simplicity	Simple, Simplistic
			Complexity	Sophisticated, Complicate
			Formality	Ergonomic, Semantics, Geometric
			Stylishness	Fashionable, Elegant, Styling, Funky
			Masculinity	Energy, Sporty, Technical, Engineering, Mechanical, Industrial
			Femininity	Romantic, Jewellery, Decorative
			General	European, Dynamic
			Unstylishness	Typical, Conservative, Uniform
		Period	50s, 60s, 80s, Traditional, Modern, Classical	
		Functional features	Adjustable, Portable, Friendly, Functional	
	Colour features	Pure, Warm, Bright		
	Physical features	Small, Middle, Thick, Heavy		
	Texture features	Sticky, Hard, Soft, Jumping, Smooth, Sharp		
	Behaviour		Childish	
	Value		High tech, Low tech, Quality, Reasonable, Reliable	
	Price		Cheap, Expensive	
	Status	Age		Young, Old, Mature, Contemporary
		Importance		Substantial, Valuable, Serious
		Components		Balanced, Loose, Integrate, Fit, Scrappy
		Origin/source		Original, Natural, Organic
Safety/stability			Speed, Fast, Safe, Strong	
General		Real, Fake		

Table 4, Categories of Objective keywords

Appropriate categories were tested against another collection of keywords which were taken from Kuno's *Colours In Context* (1999) list of 'Image words'. This represents the characteristics of colour images and expresses the characteristics of 56 themes; such as space, animals, beverages, family, friends, and so on. The other reason for adopting Kuno's work on colour is that attitudes embodied in colour such as age, personality, sex, size and so on (Danger, 1987) are almost the same as the information types used in the images' Context (see Figure 5). 'Image words' have, therefore, been used as part of the essential keywords for the system.

Carroll (1964: 97) discussed how individuals develop cognitive vocabulary: 'People vary in the degree to which they notice and concern themselves with the various kinds of attributes that characterise the things and events of the environment'. In order to make the collection of keywords more suitable for the product design professional, the list was reduced from 538 to 146 words through subjective analysis of common usage by working with my one of my supervisors, Martin Darbyshire, director of Tangerine Product Direction and Design. While this process will have eliminated words which might be used by some designers, the database will allow new words to be entered as required and hence enable personal sets of words to be established.

"It is undeniable that words have "meanings" that go above and beyond the scope of linguistic creativity which can be achieved. They often carry the weight of a person's own experience" (Bouillon and Busa, 2001: 8). Also Trask's (1995) chapter "Variation in language" addressed geographical variation, community variation, educational background variation, and sex and gender, which affect the use of vocabularies. The choice of vocabulary is highly variable, even when people try to deliver the same concept. It is therefore impossible to define an absolute set of keywords. This system focuses on providing organised, design oriented image storage and providing a well-structured image context relationship with products is of greater importance than the keywords. As the keywords can be expanded later the prototype of the database will provide an initial set of keywords in each category.

Table 5 and Table 6 show the current range of 'Image words.' Basically most keywords can fit into the categories. Words such as *positive* have been used as the names of categories. Words such as *warm* could also be included in the category of **Physical sensation** as well as **Colour features** and will be added later into appropriate categories as the system develops.

Heading Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Keyword
Subjective	Feelings	Physical sensation	Aromatic Comfortable Emotional Fragrant Moist Relaxed Silent Wild Tasteful Spicy Tangy Tranquil
		Liking	Admirable Affable Alluring Gentle Sweet
		Specificity	Distinctive Dramatic Unique Thorough
		Interestingness	Precious
		Kindness	Calm
	Positive	General	Indifferent
		Beauty	Beautiful Pretty
		Superiority	August Clever Dandy Excellent Exciting Exquisite Innovative Powerful Smart Wonderful Witty Wise
		Quality	Classic
	Negative	Happiness	Cheerful Delicate Graceful Happy
		Negative	Grim Strange Vague

Table 5, Categories of subjective “Image word”

Heading Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Keyword
Objective	Physical	Visual features	Simplicity	Earthy Plain Simple
			Complexity	Complex Complicated Elaborate
			Formality	Technical
			Stylishness	Chic Cool Elegant Fancy Funky Gaudy Refined
			Masculinity	Animated Masculine
			Femininity	Decorative Feminine
			General	Dynamic Nostalgic Rhythmical Sporty
			Unstylishness	Antiquated
			Period	Fresh Youthful Traditional
		Functional features	Functional	Friendly Open Supple
		Colour features	Colour	Bright Cold Glittering Hot Light Pure Radiant Warm Vivid Transparent Translucent
		Physical features	Physical	Dense Firm Fit Hard Heavy Humorous Sharp Shiny Small Solid Still Vast Straight
		Texture features	Texture	Coarse Rugged Smooth Soft
	Behaviour		Behaviour	Active Aggressive Confident Discreet Docile Easygoing Ingenuous Quiet
	Value		Value	Valuable
	Price		Price	Opulent Rich
	Status	Age	Age	
		Importance	Importance	Dignified Influential Prestigious Serious Substantial
		Component feature	Components	Orderly
		Origin/source	Origin/source	Ethnic Natural Organic Original Radical Primitive
		Safety/stability	Stability	
	General	General	General	Absolute, Airy, Assured, Authentic, Balanced, Basic Clear Clean Explicit Healthy Immaculate Obvious Precise Refreshing Robust Rustic Visionary Sure Volatile

Table 6, Categories of Objective “Image word”

Conclusion

The software application of the visual reference database is being developed using the structure of the three information areas: SPECIFICATION, EMOTION, and CHARACTERISTIC and will provide the product design professional with an image storage tool.

The database holds the potential to reduce the time designers spend at the concept design stage of the product development. It will also subconsciously assist designers in achieving Mono's (1997) statement that a designer should aim at understanding product language better to be able to improve his design. It will also be able to function as a cognitive database to assist designers in better understanding the target user of the product being designed.

Work on the database has generated great interest from designers and a prototype is on the test. Its development and the evaluation will be the subject of future paper.

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Appendix A

Product indexing:

For a number of years the UK Design Council maintained the Design Index, a record of some 7,000 ‘well designed’ British consumer goods. The Index, now at Brighton University, comprises a photographic record of selected products, together with their specifications, costs, and the name of the designer and manufacturer.